

Open Access and AI for Research Assessment: Identifying and Evaluating Software Mentions in Scholarly Publications

Samuel Scalbert^{1,2}, Kumar Guha¹, Laurent Romary^{1,2}

¹ *Inria, Scientific information and culture department*

² *SOFAIR*

Purpose

Open scholarly communication enables new approaches to research assessment across different stages of the scientific cycle. For instance, the scientific community in Europe is progressively adopting more transparent methods for evaluating research. Traditional bibliometric indicators, which rely on privately owned databases, lack transparency and fairness in assessing research or guiding strategic science policy decisions.

In contrast, open archive repositories and aggregators offer a rich foundation of full texts and metadata that can be leveraged with open algorithms and computations. This presents an opportunity to promote more responsible research evaluation while considering discipline-specific approaches.

In computer science, for example, conference papers are a significant part of scholarly output, even though many lack DOIs or other persistent identifiers, and are therefore excluded from conventional commercial indicators. Similarly, software and code developed by researchers are crucial contributions. Initiatives like Software Heritage aim to preserve source code, but identifying individual or collective authors remains a challenge.

Methods

In response to this challenge, and within the framework of the European GraspOS project, Inria, as a partner in the Computer Science pilot project, has developed a tool to identify software mentions in the full text of scientific publications. This tool, leveraging Grobid and Softcite, processes PDF files as input and produces an XML-TEI file for each PDF. The output file contains both the original metadata and the metadata of the software mentions identified in the full text.

Three different types of mentions are taken into account to reflect different possibilities: sharing, creating or using software. Each of them reflects the life cycle of a software, which can also be interesting information about the success of the software.

The tools can be linked to other databases. A notification process is currently being developed with the French National Publication Repository (HAL) using COAR Notify.

On the technical side, two applications are used, two dockers for the machine learning application and two clients to discuss with the containers. The result of the pipeline is a web application in Flask.

Figure 1. screenshot from the GitHub of SOFTware-Viz: *“The pipeline for all the SOFTware’s applications”*

Results

The result app allows the visualisation of software mentions for a set of PDFs. It presents the list of software identified and the type of mention found, as well as the publication's metadata, i.e. the authors and their affiliations. This creates a link between structures, authors and software thanks to the publication's metadata.

It provides a basis for the identification of software production, which will eventually be used for evaluation or candidacy for a research position.

The visualisation tool also provides two services aimed at contributing to the training of the machine learning application. The backlink to HAL, which will be tested this year, also aims to obtain more accurate feedback on the output from the authors themselves.

The tool is divided into two units which we have called SOFTware-Sync and SOFTware-viz. It also exists as a Linux based hub, SOFTware-hub. SOFTware-Sync is a Python-based application that uses libraries such as lxml and BeautifulSoup. It synchronises the output of Grobid and Softcite. Grobid processes the PDF and converts it into an XML-TEI file, including the original metadata from HAL, the metadata extracted from the PDF, and the full text of the PDF. It then inserts the software mentions identified by Softcite into the full text, creating an XML file that combines the metadata from HAL, the full text from Grobid, and the software mentions from Softcite.

It offers several features including: enriching XML files with corresponding JSON data, flexible enhancement options such as project-specific tagging or focusing only on documents containing software mentions, data consistency checking to detect any errors in processing a file, csv reports, quality control for missing values.

A web application uses the JSON output from Softcite to create an ArangoDB for visualisation.

SOFTWARE-viz was developed to test the whole tool, based on INRIA PDF documents deposited in the HAL Open Archive. It is based on the XML-TEI format. Another version,

"SOFTWARE-VIZ-LIGHT" , was created to allow a wider integration with other open source platforms.

Figure 2. screenshot from the SOFTWARE-VIZ application dashboard

The visualisation application presents a dashboard showing software mentions according to their attributes (created/used/shared) and the publications linked to each mention. For each document, two pages are available: for the whole document, it lists all the mentions and the context in which they were found; for a specific software, it lists only the mentions and the context of this software, as well as all the other software cited in this document. The "Software" page shows the timeline of citations, the list of top authors, structures and documents that cite this software the most, and the list of all documents that cite this software. An "Authors" page allows you to search for an author in order to visualise the software linked to this author through his/her publication. A "Disambiguate" page displays the software names that are most likely to be disambiguated.

The Linux-based hub aims to allow the entire pipeline to be started with a single command. It uses Python and shell scripts. With minimal requirements, it is possible to download and run the whole tool from github. The Hub automatically installs all the necessary elements (Docker images, etc.), automatically processes the PDFs provided and creates the visualisation pages.

Through our collaboration with HAL, we aim to address the challenge of disambiguating software mentions. HAL will enable authors to directly clarify and complete any missing or incomplete software references in their publications. This process will help us build a comprehensive database that maps relationships between teams/authors and the software they use or develop. With this database, we can identify and account for any previously overlooked software mentions, ensuring more accurate and complete records. Furthermore, by disambiguating the software mentions by the author, we would be able to automatically generate training data for the recognition of software mentions.

Value

The innovative aspect of this work is the quality improvement of the softcite programme. Softcite output is enhanced with Grobid output and the result is cleaned and ordered before being made available for visualisation and review. In addition, unlike commercially based tools, it is based on open source solutions and is itself open source and freely available for use, adaptation or extension. The Hub allows easy integration into environments other than the one used for testing. To our knowledge, there is no other tool available for this purpose. We also found that this tool does not only serve the purpose of identifying software produced or shared by research teams or researchers. It also provides an interesting insight into the 'life cycle' of software citations (and hence software popularity?) over time. The disambiguation process will allow us to enhance the result of Softcite, by automatically generating training data with the help of the authors.

Limitations. As this tool is new, there is always room for improvement. During testing in 2024, we noticed a need to improve mention attributes. Some "shared" mentions were incorrectly qualified as "used" or vice versa. Also, we have not yet been able to test the Hub in the "real world" , so it is not yet ready for distribution. Finally, a comparison between the software declared by the Inria research teams during the test and the software found by SOFTWARE-Sync showed that a number of software appearing in the latter may have been overlooked by the teams as a major output. However, we were unable to obtain sufficient feedback to confirm this.

Perspectives. The training of machine learning in the European SOFAIR project has been significantly improved this winter 24/25, allowing for more consistent results. We hope that this tool will provide a better means of assessing the software output of researchers in computer science, but perhaps also in other fields, as software is being developed in an increasing number of research communities.

References

- Scalbert, S. (n.d.). *SOFTware-Viz* [GitHub repository]. GitHub. <https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTware-Viz>
- Scalbert, S. (n.d.). *SOFTware-Viz-Light* [GitHub repository]. GitHub. <https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTware-Viz-Light>
- Scalbert, S. (n.d.). *SOFTware-Sync* [GitHub repository]. GitHub. <https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTware-Sync>
- Scalbert, S. (n.d.). *SOFTware-Hub* [GitHub repository]. GitHub. <https://github.com/Samuel-Scalbert/SOFTware-Hub>
- GraspOS projet: <https://graspos.eu/>
- Angelo Di Iorio, Kumar Guha, Silvio Peroni, Laurent Romary, Thanasis Vergoulis. Pilot analysis - Computer Science. 2023. (hal-04362464)
- SOFAIR project, Making Software FAIR: A machine-assisted workflow for the research software lifecycle: <https://sofair.org/>